

1.1. The project summary

Project Number ¹	101003532	Project Acronym ²	Sol-Rec2
One form per project			
General information			
Project title ³	Innovative digital watermarks and green solvents for the recovery and recycling of multi-layer materials		
Starting date ⁴	01/06/2021		
Duration in months ⁵	36		
Call (part) identifier ⁶	H2020-SC5-2020-2		
Topic	CE-SC5-24-2020 Improving the sorting, separation and recycling of composite and multi-layer materials		
Fixed EC Keywords	Circular economy		
Free keywords	Circular economy; sustainability; recycling; laminate packaging; blister pack; multi-layer materials; ionic liquid; deep eutectic solvent; digital watermark; polyethylene; polypropylene; PVC		
Abstract ⁷			
<p>This 36-month Sol-Rec2 project targets the development and implementation of ground-breaking strategies for improving the sorting, separation and recycling of pharma blister packs and laminate consumer packaging waste consisting of multiple layers of polymers and aluminium. Innovative digital watermark technologies will be further developed and progressed to TRL6 through successful demonstration of rapid and efficient sorting of multi-layer packaging.</p> <p>Experience from working in the field of ionic liquids will be leveraged to develop a toolbox of novel green solvent systems (TRL5) that can delaminate multi-layer packaging material and selectively dissolve target polymers – reducing demand for virgin raw materials through efficient separation and recovery of high purity PE, PP and PVC polymers and aluminium. Socioeconomic and environmental benefits of Sol-Rec2 will be established through detailed life cycle analyses.</p> <p>An exciting consortium of SMEs, research organisations and universities from 6 EU countries has been established, consisting of IPM2 (FR-SME), Aimplas (ES-RTO), FiliGrade (NL-SME), TWI (UK-RTO), University of Leicester (UK-UNI), Solvionic (FR-SME), Plastigram (CZ-SME) and Mikrolin (HU-SME). Partners bring a wealth of experience to the project covering plastic waste collection and sorting, digital watermarks, ionic liquids, polymer dissolution, recycling of multi-layer materials, reuse of polymers, eco-design and life cycle assessments. Generated knowledge will help to accelerate innovative recycling within Eastern Europe and reduce the complexity of multi-layer materials, leading to the design of more sustainable laminate packaging.</p> <p>Sol-Rec2 will deliver sustainable production of high purity polymers and aluminium – providing recyclers with a valuable income stream, minimising the environmental impact and carbon footprint associated with virgin plastics production and bauxite mining whilst also making a valuable contribution to the circular economy.</p>			

1.2. List of Beneficiaries

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List of Beneficiaries

No	Name	Short name	Country	Project entry month ⁸	Project exit month
1	INTERNATIONAL PROJECT MANAGEMENT PLATING ET MATERIALS SARL	IPM2	France	1	36
2	AIMPLAS - ASOCIACION DE INVESTIGACION DE MATERIALES PLASTICOS Y CONEXAS	AIM	Spain	1	36
3	FILIGRADE SUSTAINABLE WATERMARKS BV	FIL	Netherlands	1	36
4	TWI LIMITED	TWI	United Kingdom	1	36
5	UNIVERSITY OF LEICESTER	ULEIC	United Kingdom	1	36
6	SOLVIONIC	SOL	France	1	36
7	PLASTIGRAM INDUSTRIES A.S.	PLA	Czech Republic	1	36
8	MIKROLIN HUNGARY TERMELO ES SZOLGALTATO KFT	MIK	Hungary	1	36